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Improving MPI communication latency of Euroben kernels

Chandan Basu^a

National Supercomputer Center, Linköping University, Linköping 581 83, Sweden

Abstract

A new MPI_Alltoallv algorithm is tested on the Euroben kernel routine mod2f. The new MPI_Alltoallv routine utilizes the high bandwidth within a node more effectively and puts less stress on inter node bandwidth. The MPI_Alltoallv is achieved first by inter-node communication and then followed by intra-node communication. A comparison of the modified mod2f with the original mod2f is made for different data sizes and run sizes on CURIE system. The results show substantial improvement using the modified MPI_Alltoallv on CURIE system

1. Introduction

On modern clusters with many-core / multi-core nodes there are large differences in bandwidth and latency between cores in the same node and cores across different nodes. This leads to a non-uniform network topology for MPI processes w.r.t. bandwidth and latency. Moreover in many cluster configurations a node has single interconnect cable going out for connecting with other nodes. It can create a blocking configuration for MPI communication. As an example on a 32 core node if all the MPI ranks try to communicate outside node through a single interconnect cable it can create a 1:32 blocking situation. This might impact the data transfer rate and consequently the scalability of codes. On such systems network unaware MPI programs can create network congestion. Thus it is important to write algorithms which exploit intra-node bandwidth / latency more efficiently and less reliant on inter-node bandwidth / latency.

^a Corresponding author. *E-mail address:* cbasu@nsc.liu.se

It is generally considered difficult to introduce network awareness in application programs. However many parallel programs are heavily dependent on MPI collective calls. The MPI communication latency is an important factor in scalability and performance of many parallel programs. The performance of MPI collective calls can be improved if these collectives are network aware. There are some efforts in recent times to make MPI programs topology aware [1-3]. In the PRACE-1IP WP7.5D project - “Improving MPI communication latency on Euroben kernels” we have developed a network aware *MPI_Alltoallv* routine. This routine is applied on the *mod2f* kernel in Euroben benchmark suite [4]. The performance of the *mod2f* kernel is heavily dependent on *MPI_Alltoallv* routine. We replace the standard *MPI_Alltoallv* with our network aware *MPI_Alltoallv* routine. Our results show that the performance of *mod2f* improves with the network aware *MPI_Alltoallv*.

2. Description of mod2f kernel

Euroben benchmark suite is a large collection of benchmark programs developed under PRACE project for benchmarking HPC systems for a wide variety of hardware platforms. The C-MPI branch of Euroben benchmark is of our interest. We have chosen *mod2f* kernel from Euroben benchmark suite. The *mod2f* routine is a 1-D Fast Fourier Transform (FFT). The C-MPI version of *mod2f* program does FFT of distributed arrays.

The *mod2f* source code is placed under `euoben-ports/base/C-MPI/mod2f` folder. There is a Makefile in this folder for compiling the benchmark. After compilation the input parameters are specified in a file called `mod2f.in`.

The main communication overhead in *mod2f* comes from a routine called *gtrans*. This routine does a global transposition of arrays. To achieve global transpose *gtrans* calls *MPI_Alltoallv* routine. As is well known *MPI_Alltoall* / *MPI_Alltoallv* is a very communication intensive MPI call and consequently does not scale well. The code while running prints out communication overhead which shows that most of the time is spent in communication routines.

3. Modified All2all

For our approach we need to write a tuned all-to-all routine. Here we describe our network aware all-to-all routine.

3.1. INTRA and INTER node communicators

In order to do our modifications we need to create *INTRA* and *INTER* node communicators. The *INTRA* node communicator has ranks from the same node. The *INTER* node communicator has ranks from different nodes. The global communicator is split into *INTRA* and *INTER* node communicators. In order to form these communicators, we need to assign colors and keys (i.e., identities across the nodes and within the nodes respectively) to every MPI process. We define

$$color = rank/NPE$$

$$key = mod(rank, NPE)$$

where NPE is the number of cores / node, rank is the rank obtained from `MPI_COMM_WORLD`. The `mpirun` is invoked such that ranks in a node are consecutive and total number of ranks are integer multiples of NPE. Once the color and the key is assigned, simple splitting of `MPI_COMM_WORLD` along same color results in formation of the *INTRA* communicator. This is achieved by calling `MPI_Comm_split` routine and passing to it `MPI_COMM_WORLD`, color and key as 1st, 2nd and 3rd argument respectively. The c call looks like:

```
MPI_Comm_split(MPI_COMM_WORLD, color, key, &INTRA);
```

The splitting of *MPI_COMM_WORLD* along same *key* results in formation of the *INTER* communicator. This is achieved by calling *MPI_Comm_split* routine and passing to it *MPI_COMM_WORLD*, *key* and *color* as 1st, 2nd and 3rd argument respectively. The c call looks like:

```
MPI_Comm_split(MPI_COMM_WORLD, key, color, &INTER);
```

In Fig 1 we show a graphical representation of the *INTRA* and *INTER* communicators.

Fig. 1. Intra and inter node communicators

When the communicators are set up this way all the communication over *INTRA* will be confined within the node and all the communication over *INTER* will be across nodes. We have created a routine called *GMPI_Init()* which initializes MPI and also *INTRA* and *INTER* communicator.

3.2. *MPI_Alltoallv_tuned* algorithm

In *MPI_Alltoallv* each rank *i* sends data to each rank *j* where *i* and *j* vary from 0 to *np - 1*, *np* being the total number of processes. To keep track of number of elements to be sent and their location in the send buffer each rank keeps respective send and displacement arrays called *scnt* and *sdis* respectively. The *i*-th element of *scnt* and *sdis* gives the number of elements and its starting location in the send buffer to be sent to the *i*-th rank. Similarly each rank keeps track of number of elements to be received and their location in the receive buffer through *rcnt* and *rdis* arrays respectively. The *i*-th element of *rcnt* and *rdis* gives the number of elements and its starting location in the receive buffer to be received from the *i*-th rank

In *MPI_Alltoallv_tuned* we divide the *MPI_Alltoallv* in two steps. First each rank sends / receives data across *INTER* communicator. Each rank divides its send buffer into bigger chunks and corresponding displacements respectively called *scnt_inter* and *sdis_inter*. The *i*-th element of *scnt_inter* is the number of elements sent to the partner process in *i*-th node and is sum of all the *scnt* elements for the *i*-th node from the sender rank, where *i* varies from 0 to *np/NPE*. Similarly we calculate *rcnt_inter* and *rdis_inter* where the *i*-th element of *rcnt_inter* is the sum of all the receives from the partner process in *i*-th node for the receiver node. We first do *MPI_Alltoallv* over *INTER* communicator with these counts. The c interface looks like:

```
MPI_Alltoallv(sbuf, scnt_inter, sdis_inter, MPI_DOUBLE, rbuf, rcnt_inter, rdis_inter, MPI_DOUBLE,
INTER);
```

As each rank is involved this results in *NPE* simultaneous *MPI_Alltoallv* each sending data to its partner ranks in other nodes. This step involves communication across nodes. Once this step is over all the nodes have the data to be received from other nodes. However from the individual process perspective these buffers are not in right place. These data are stored in temporary buffers. Next we need to exchange these temporary buffers among processes in the same node to put them in right place in the final receive buffer. This is achieved by *NPE* number of *MPI_Alltoallv* over *INTRA* communicator with appropriate send / receive / displacement counts. In this stage all the communication is within node. Also these communications run concurrently in each node without using the external network.

The computation of intermediate send / receive / displacement counts are quite complicated. We have created a routine called *gr_countv* which computes all the intermediate send / receive / displacement counts from original *scnt*, *sdis*, *rcnt*, *rdis* relevant for *MPI_Alltoallv*.

4. Modification of the *mod2f* code

4.1. Change in the structure of the original code

We need to do a change in the structure of the original code to achieve better efficiency. The original *mod2f* program has a main loop which is timed like:

```
time1 = MPI_Wtime();
for( irep = 1; irep <= nrep; irep++ ) {
    ... some serial computation ...
    gtrans( ... input parameters ... );
    ... some serial computation ...
    gtrans( ... input parameters ... );
    ... some serial computation ...
    gtrans( ... input parameters ... );
    ... some serial computation ...
}
time1 = MPI_Wtime() - time1;
```

The routine *gtrans* does a global transposition of arrays. To achieve global transpose *gtrans* calls *MPI_Alltoallv* routine. In the original version of *mod2f* *scnt*, *sdis*, *rcnt*, *rdis* arrays are calculated within *gtrans*. However these counts do not change for a particular FFT operation and hence it is sufficient to calculate these once outside the “for loop”. We have done this change in the original code. This is particularly important for our approach as in our case computation of intermediate send / receive / buffers are more complex and will have significant overhead if computed every time within *gtrans*. However if they are moved outside the “for loop” their overhead is negligible.

4.2. Modification of the *mod2f* program

Our main modification is related to replacing *MPI_Alltoallv* with *MPI_Alltoallv_tune* routine. We do not change the algorithm of *mod2f* in any way. However the interface of *MPI_Alltoallv_tune* is not exactly same as *MPI_Alltoallv*. To pass right arguments to *MPI_Alltoallv_tune* we need to initialize few data structures initially. These initializations are done before the timing loop starts. At each place where we make changes the changed and original codes are both kept as:

```
#ifdef GRP // SNIC-LIU modification
```

```
new things
#else
original things
#endif
```

Where GRP is the preprocessor flag to activate the changed region. The *MPI_Alltoally_tune* and few other related routines are kept in a file named *tmpi.c*. The Makefile is modified accordingly to compile and link this file with *mod2f*. The *mod2f* program has a correctness checking and the results show that the program is working correctly with our modifications.

5. Results and discussions

5.1. Running the code

We have compiled our code on CURIE with Intel compiler version 12.1.7.256 and bullxmpi version 1.1.8.1. We compile two binaries with or without our changes respectively. For our runs it is important to have consecutive ranks in a node. We do this by creating a hostfile with node names in which each node name is consecutively repeated NPE number of times. This hostfile is given to the mpirun to spawn jobs with consecutive ranks in a node. We have created a run-script which first writes the hostfile as described above and then the mpirun is invoked with the hostfile given to mpirun.

5.2. Results

We run *mod2f* on CURIE. In the CURIE system each node has 32 CPU cores (NPE = 32). As we are trying to see the effects of network on the scaling we choose larger problems and run them over many nodes. We choose array length of 1048576 and 4194304. For each size we run it from 256 ranks to 1024 ranks. The results of our runs are shown in Figs 2 and 3. In Figs 2 and 3 the red lines represent the original *mod2f* run while the blue lines represent the modified *mod2f* run. As can be seen from the graphs the modified versions are running much faster when the number of nodes are higher. As can be seen from the figures for our cases the FFT time does not increase much with increase in number of processes. For an array of size 1048576 elements FFT time for the modified *mod2f* run on 256 and 1024 cores are 0.01 sec and 0.06 sec respectively whereas the FFT time for the unmodified *mod2f* run on 256 and 1024 cores are 0.08 sec and 0.65 sec respectively. Similarly for an array of size 4194304 elements FFT time for the modified *mod2f* run on 256 and 1024 cores are 0.02 sec and 0.07 sec respectively whereas the FFT time for the unmodified *mod2f* run on 256 and 1024 cores are 0.09 sec and 0.7 sec respectively. The FFT speed however does not improve with increasing processes in either of the cases. In a real program, there will be other computations along with FFT and thus our approach can lead to better scaling as the FFT overhead will be less.

Fig. 2. FFT time for array of length 1048576

Fig. 3. FFT time for array of length 4194304

6. Conclusion

We have developed a tuned version of *MPI_Alltoallv* routine and applied to a benchmark program called *mod2f*. The results show considerable improvement in performance. This method will be particularly efficient when small amount of data is exchanged frequently. The current version has few limitations, e.g., it works only for double

precision variables, it can be applied on *MPI_COMM_WORLD*, total number of MPI processes should be divisible by *NPE* etc. However these are limitations of current implementation and can be generalized further. The tuned All-to-all routine can be applied to other programs also with minimal code modification.

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List of Appendixes

Appendix 1: Source code listing of tmpic.c containing MPI_Alltoallv_tuned and other related routines

Appendix 2: Source code listing of tmpic.h containing function prototypes and data structures

Appendix 3: Source code listing of modified mod2f.c

Appendix 4: Source code listing of modified gtrans.c

Appendix 1

```
// NSC, LIU optimized collective routines
```

```
#include "tmpic.h"
```

```
int GMPI_Init(){
    int ierr, equal;
    int rank, np, color, key, leng, i;
    int my_intra_rank, my_inter_rank;
    int my_intra_size, my_inter_size;
    char *ch, *charr;

    MPI_Init(0,0);
    MPI_Comm_rank(MPI_COMM_WORLD, &rank);
    MPI_Comm_size(MPI_COMM_WORLD, &np);
    GMPI_COMM_WORLD.globl_comm=MPI_COMM_WORLD;
    color = rank / (G_SIZE_INTRA);
    key = rank % G_SIZE_INTRA;
    MPI_Comm_split(MPI_COMM_WORLD, color, key, &GMPI_COMM_WORLD.intra_comm);
    MPI_Comm_split(MPI_COMM_WORLD, key, color, &GMPI_COMM_WORLD.inter_comm);
    MPI_Comm_rank(GMPI_COMM_WORLD.globl_comm, &GMPI_COMM_WORLD.globl_rank);
    MPI_Comm_rank(GMPI_COMM_WORLD.intra_comm, &GMPI_COMM_WORLD.intra_rank);
    MPI_Comm_rank(GMPI_COMM_WORLD.inter_comm, &GMPI_COMM_WORLD.inter_rank);
    MPI_Comm_size(GMPI_COMM_WORLD.globl_comm, &GMPI_COMM_WORLD.globl_size);
    MPI_Comm_size(GMPI_COMM_WORLD.intra_comm, &GMPI_COMM_WORLD.intra_size);
    MPI_Comm_size(GMPI_COMM_WORLD.inter_comm, &GMPI_COMM_WORLD.inter_size);
    ch = (char *)malloc(100*sizeof(char));
    charr = (char *)malloc(100*G_SIZE_INTRA*sizeof(char));

    MPI_Get_processor_name(ch, &leng);
    leng = 100;
    MPI_Allgather(ch, leng, MPI_CHAR, charr, leng, MPI_CHAR, GMPI_COMM_WORLD.intra_comm);
    strncpy(ch,charr, leng);
    for (i = 0; i < G_SIZE_INTRA; i++) {
        equal = strcmp (ch, &charr[i*leng], leng);
        if (equal != 0) {
            printf("wrong group formation\n");
            exit(EXIT_FAILURE);
        }
    }
    free(ch);
    free(charr);
    return 1;
}

int getrand(int min,int max){
    if (min == max)
        return min;
    else
        return(rand()%(max-min)+min);
}
```

```

int sum(int *num_array1, int leng) {
int total=0;
int a=0;
for(a=0; a<leng; a++) {
    total = total + num_array1[a];
}
return(total);
}

float frand()
{
    return -1+2*((float)rand())/RAND_MAX;
} // end frand()

int maxval(int *b,int n)
{
    int c, max;
    max=b[0];
    for(c=1; c<n; c++)
    {
        if(max<b[c])
            max=b[c];
    }
    return max;
} //end of function

void allocate_ptarr(int np, int ng) {
    int i;
    gr_scnt.intra = (int *)malloc(np*sizeof(int));
    gr_scnt.inter = (int *)malloc(ng*sizeof(int));
    gr_scnt.globl = (int *)malloc(np*sizeof(int));

    gr_sdis.intra = (int *)malloc(np*sizeof(int));
    gr_sdis.inter = (int *)malloc(ng*sizeof(int));
    gr_sdis.globl = (int *)malloc(np*sizeof(int));

    gr_rcnt.intra = (int *)malloc(np*sizeof(int));
    gr_rcnt.inter = (int *)malloc(ng*sizeof(int));
    gr_rcnt.globl = (int *)malloc(np*sizeof(int));

    gr_rdis.intra = (int *)malloc(np*sizeof(int));
    gr_rdis.inter = (int *)malloc(ng*sizeof(int));
    gr_rdis.globl = (int *)malloc(np*sizeof(int));

    for (i = 0; i < np; i++) {
        gr_scnt.intra[i] = 0;
        gr_sdis.intra[i] = 0;
        gr_rcnt.intra[i] = 0;
        gr_rdis.intra[i] = 0;
        gr_scnt.globl[i] = 0;
        gr_sdis.globl[i] = 0;
        gr_rcnt.globl[i] = 0;
    }
}

```

```

    gr_rdis.globl[i] = 0;
}
for (i = 0; i < ng; i++) {
    gr_scnt.inter[i] = 0;
    gr_sdis.inter[i] = 0;
    gr_rcnt.inter[i] = 0;
    gr_rdis.inter[i] = 0;
}
gr_scnt.maxv = 0.0;
gr_rcnt.maxv = 0.0;
gr_sdis.maxv = 0.0;
gr_rdis.maxv = 0.0;
}

```

```

void deallocate_ptarr(){
    free(gr_scnt.intra);
    free(gr_scnt.inter);
    free(gr_scnt.globl);
    free(gr_rcnt.intra);
    free(gr_rcnt.inter);
    free(gr_rcnt.globl);
    free(gr_sdis.intra);
    free(gr_sdis.inter);
    free(gr_sdis.globl);
    free(gr_rdis.intra);
    free(gr_rdis.inter);
    free(gr_rdis.globl);
}

```

```

void gr_countv(int *scnt, int *sdis, int *rcnt, int *rdis, gcom com) {
    int i, j, k, err, gs_max;
    for (i = 0; i < com.inter_size; i++){
        gr_scnt.inter[i] = 0;
        for (j = 0; j < com.intra_size; j++){
            k = (i-0) * com.intra_size + j;
            gr_scnt.inter[i] = gr_scnt.inter[i] + scnt[k];
        }
    }
    MPI_Alltoall(gr_scnt.inter, 1, MPI_INT, gr_rcnt.inter, 1, MPI_INT, com.inter_comm);
    gr_sdis.inter[0] = 0;
    gr_rdis.inter[0] = 0;
    for(i = 1; i < com.inter_size; i++){
        gr_sdis.inter[i] = gr_sdis.inter[i-1] + gr_scnt.inter[i-1];
        gr_rdis.inter[i] = gr_rdis.inter[i-1] + gr_rcnt.inter[i-1];
    }
    MPI_Alltoall(scnt, GSIZE_INTRA, MPI_INT, gr_scnt.intra, GSIZE_INTRA, MPI_INT, com.inter_comm);
    for(i = 0; i < com.globl_size; i++){
        gr_rcnt.intra[i] = rcnt[i];
        gr_rdis.intra[i] = rdis[i];
    }
    gr_sdis.intra[0] = 0;
    for(i = 1; i < com.globl_size; i++)
        gr_sdis.intra[i] = gr_sdis.intra[i-1] + gr_scnt.intra[i-1];
}

```

```

for(i = 0; i < com.globl_size; i++) {
  gr_sdis.globl[i] = sdis[i];
  gr_scnt.globl[i] = scnt[i];
}
gs_max = maxval(gr_scnt.intra, com.globl_size);
MPI_Allreduce(&gs_max, &gr_scnt.maxv, 1, MPI_INT, MPI_MAX, com.globl_comm);
}

int MPI_Alltoallv_tuned(double *sbuf, ptarr scnt, ptarr sdis, double *rbuf, ptarr rcnt, ptarr rdis, gcom comm) {
int ierr;
double *rbuf_temp;
int i, j, k, l, rcnt_temp;

if(comm.inter_size == 1) //use noraml all2all
  MPI_Alltoallv(sbuf, scnt.globl, sdis.globl, MPI_D, rbuf, rcnt.intra, rdis.intra, MPI_D, comm.globl_comm);
else if (scnt.maxv > GMPI_TO_MPI_V) //!use normal all2allv for large data
  MPI_Alltoallv(sbuf, scnt.globl, sdis.globl, MPI_D, rbuf, rcnt.intra, rdis.intra, MPI_D, comm.globl_comm);
else { //use group based all2all
  rcnt_temp = sum(rcnt.intra, comm.inter_size);
  //rbuf_temp = (double *)malloc(rcnt_temp*sizeof(double));
  rbuf_temp = work_buf;
  MPI_Alltoallv(sbuf, scnt.intra, sdis.intra, MPI_D, rbuf_temp, rcnt.intra, rdis.intra, MPI_D, comm.inter_comm);
  j = 1;
  for(i=0; i<comm.inter_size; i++){
    k = rdis.intra[i];
    l = rcnt.intra[i];
    j = (i-0) * comm.intra_size;
    MPI_Alltoallv(rbuf_temp, &scnt.intra[j], &sdis.intra[j], MPI_D, rbuf, &rcnt.intra[j], &rdis.intra[j], MPI_D,
comm.intra_comm);
  }
  //free(rbuf_temp);
}
return ierr=1;
}

```

```

#if 0

```

```

subroutine MPI_Alltoall_tuned (sbuf, incr, dtype, rbuf, comm, ierr)
double precision :: sbuf(:), rbuf(:)
integer :: ierr
type(pt) :: incr
type(gcom) :: comm
integer :: dtype
double precision, allocatable, dimension(:) :: rbuf_temp
integer :: i, k
if(comm%inter_size == 1) then !use noraml all2all
  call MPI_Alltoall(sbuf, incr%intra, dtype, rbuf, &
& incr%intra, dtype, comm%intra_comm, ierr)
else if (incr%intra > GMPI_TO_MPI) then !use normal all2all for large data
  call MPI_Alltoall(sbuf, incr%intra, dtype, rbuf, &
& incr%intra, dtype, comm%globl_comm, ierr)

```

```

else
    !use group based all2all
    allocate (rbuf_temp(incr%inter*comm%inter_size))
    call MPI_Alltoall(sbuf, incr%inter, dtype, rbuf_temp, &
    & incr%inter, dtype, comm%inter_comm, ierr)
    k = 1
    do i = 1, comm%inter_size
        call MPI_Alltoall(rbuf_temp(k), incr%intra, dtype, &
        & rbuf(k), incr%intra, dtype, &
        & comm%intra_comm, ierr)
        k = k + incr%inter
    end do
    deallocate(rbuf_temp)
endif
end subroutine MPI_Alltoall_tuned

subroutine gr_count(cnt, gr_cnt, gr_com)
integer      :: cnt
type(pt)    :: gr_cnt
type(gcom)  :: gr_com

gr_cnt%inter = cnt * gr_com%intra_size
gr_cnt%intra = cnt
end subroutine gr_count
subroutine dummy(comm)
type(gcom)    :: comm
double precision  :: buf1(10000),buf2(10000)
integer          :: ierr, incr

incr = 1
call MPI_Alltoall(buf1, incr, MPI_DOUBLE_PRECISION, buf2, incr, MPI_DOUBLE_PRECISION, comm
%globl_comm, ierr)
call MPI_Alltoall(buf1, incr, MPI_DOUBLE_PRECISION, buf2, incr, MPI_DOUBLE_PRECISION, comm
%inter_comm, ierr)
call MPI_Alltoall(buf1, incr, MPI_DOUBLE_PRECISION, buf2, incr, MPI_DOUBLE_PRECISION, comm
%intra_comm, ierr)
end subroutine dummy

#endif

```

Appendix 2

```
// NSC, LIU header for optimized collective
#include <stdio.h>
#include <string.h>
#include <stdlib.h>
#include <unistd.h>
#include <time.h>
#include "mpi.h"

#define GSIZE_INTRA 32
#define GMPI_TO_MPI 2000
#define GMPI_TO_MPI_V GMPI_TO_MPI
#define MPI_D MPI_DOUBLE_PRECISION

typedef struct {
    int intra;
    char inter;
} pt;

typedef struct {
    int *intra;
    int *inter;
    int *globl;
    int maxv;
} ptarr;

typedef struct {
    MPI_Comm globl_comm;
    MPI_Comm intra_comm;
    MPI_Comm inter_comm;
    int globl_size;
    int intra_size;
    int inter_size;
    int globl_rank;
    int intra_rank;
    int inter_rank;
} gcom;

int GMPI_init(void);
int getrand(int, int);
int sum(int *, int);
void allocate_ptarr(int, int);
void deallocate_ptarr(void);
void gr_countv(int *, int *, int *, int *, gcom);
float frand(void);
int MPI_Alltoallv_tuned(double *, ptarr, ptarr, double *, ptarr, ptarr, gcom);
int maxval(int *,int);

gcom GMPI_COMM_WORLD;
ptarr gr_scnt, gr_rcnt, gr_sdis, gr_rdis;
double work_buf[100000000];
```

Appendix 3

```
#include <stdio.h>
#include <stdlib.h>
#include <math.h>
#ifdef GRP // SNIC-LIU modification
#include "tmpic.h"
#else
#include <mpi.h>
#endif
#include "fundefs.h"
#define MAXNOD 1000000

int me, nodes;
int offset[MAXNOD][2], sizes[MAXNOD][2];
int *scnts, *sdpls, *rcnts, *rdpls;

int main( int argc, char* argv[] )
{
    MPI_Comm comm = MPI_COMM_WORLD;
    int m, n, nrep;
    int mflint, mfltrn, ok, gok;
    int i, irep, m1, m2, mc, mr, nc, nr, nx;
    double **arr1r, **arr1i, **arr2r, **arr2i, **carr, **cari;
    double *ur, *ui, *wr, *wi;
    double corr, err, frac, mflops, time1, gtime1, time2, gtime2;
    FILE *inl;
// -----
#ifdef GRP // SNIC-LIU modification
    GMPI_Init();
#else
    MPI_Init( &argc, &argv );
#endif
    MPI_Comm_rank( comm, &me );
    MPI_Comm_size( comm, &nodes );
    if ( me == 0 ) {
        state( "mod2f" );
        prthead( nodes );
    }
    inl = fopen( "mod2f.in", "r" );
    while( ( fscanf( inl, "%d%d\n", &n, &nrep ) != EOF ) ){
        m = ilog2( n );
        m2 = m/2;
        m1 = m%2 == 0 ? m2 : m2 + 1;
        nc = pow( 2, m2 );
        nr = pow( 2, m1 );
        sizoff( nr, nc );
        nx = nc > nr ? nc : nr;
        mr = nr/nodes;
        mc = nc/nodes;
// -----
// --- Check that No. of processes matches the problem size.
```

```

tstinp( mc, mr, nc, nr, me, nodes );

err = ( 10.0*n*m )* 1.0e-10;    // --- Allowed error tolerance.
// -----
// --- Allocate partitioned arrays and generate data.

carr = makmat( mr, nc ); cari = makmat( mr, nc );
arr1r = makmat( mr, nc ); arr1i = makmat( mr, nc );
arr2r = makmat( mc, nr ); arr2i = makmat( mc, nr );
ur = calloc( nx, sizeof ( double ) );
ui = calloc( nx, sizeof ( double ) );
wr = calloc( nx, sizeof ( double ) );
wi = calloc( nx, sizeof ( double ) );
gendat( mr, nc, carr, cari );
// SNIC-LIU modification. The below part is moved out of gtrans
// routine. #####

scnts = calloc( nodes, sizeof( int ) );
sdpls = calloc( nodes, sizeof( int ) );
rcnts = calloc( nodes, sizeof( int ) );
rdpls = calloc( nodes, sizeof( int ) );
cntdpls( scnts, sdpls, rcnts, rdpls, 0 );
// #####

#ifdef GRP // SNIC-LIU modification
    allocate_ptarr(nodes, GMPI_COMM_WORLD.inter_size);
    gr_countv(scnts, sdpls, rcnts, rdpls, GMPI_COMM_WORLD);
#endif
    time1 = MPI_Wtime();
    time2 = 0.0;
// -----
//--- Repeat FFT 'nrep' times for this problem size and do timing.
    for( irep = 1; irep <= nrep; irep++ ) {
        cp_arr2d( mr, nc, carr, arr1r );
        cp_arr2d( mr, nc, cari, arr1i );
// -----
//--- Do 1st transposition.

        gtrans( nr, nc, sizes[me][0], sizes[me][1],
                arr1r, arr1i, arr2r, arr2i, 0, &time2 );
// -----
//--- Do 1st pass of MC NR-length FFTs per processor.

        cfft4( 0, m1, ur, ui, arr2r[0], arr2i[0], wr, wi );
        for( i = 0; i < mc; i++ ) {
            cfft4( 1, m1, ur, ui, arr2r[i], arr2i[i], wr, wi );
        }
// -----
//--- Multiply with twiddle factors.

        twiddle( mc, nr, arr2r, arr2i );
// -----
//--- Do 2nd transposition.

```

```

    gtrans( nc, nr, sizes[me][1], sizes[me][0],
           arr2r, arr2i, arr1r, arr1i, 1, &time2 );
//-----
//--- Do 2nd pass of MR NC-length FFTs per processor.

    cfft4( 0, m2, ur, ui, arr1r[0], arr1i[0], wr, wi );
    for( i = 0; i < mr; i++ ) {
        cfft4( 1, m2, ur, ui, arr1r[i], arr1i[i], wr, wi );
    }
//-----
//--- Do 3rd transposition.

    gtrans( nr, nc, sizes[me][0], sizes[me][1],
           arr1r, arr1i, arr2r, arr2i, 0, &time2 );
}
time1 = MPI_Wtime() - time1;
#ifdef GRP // SNIC-LIU modification
    deallocate_ptarr();
#endif
// SNIC-LIU modification. The below part is moved out of gtrans
// routine. #####
    free( scnts ); free( sdpls ); free( rcnts ); free( rdpls );
// #####

// -----
// --- Check for errors and correct timing for filling of arrays.

    ok = check( mc, nr, arr2r, arr2i, err );
    corr = MPI_Wtime();
    for( irep = 0; i < nrep; i++ ) {
        cp_arr2d( mr, nc, carr, arr1r );
        cp_arr2d( mr, nc, cari, arr1i );
    }
    corr = MPI_Wtime() - corr;
    time1 = time1 - corr;
    MPI_Reduce( &time1, &gtime1, 1, MPI_DOUBLE, MPI_MAX, 0, comm );
    time1 = gtime1/(double)nrep;
    MPI_Reduce( &time2, &gtime2, 1, MPI_DOUBLE, MPI_MAX, 0, comm );
    time2 = gtime2/(double)nrep;
// -----
// --- Calculate Mflop rates.

    if ( me == 0 ) {
        nflops( m, &mflint, &mfltrn );
        mflops = 1.0e-6*( mflint + mfltrn )/gtime1;
        frac = 100.0*(time2/time1);
        prtspeed( n, time1, mflops, time2, frac, ok );
    }
    free( wi ); free( wr );
    free( ui ); free( ur );
    delmat( mc, arr2i ); delmat( mc, arr2r );
    delmat( mr, arr1i ); delmat( mr, arr1r );

```

```
    delmat( mr, cari ); delmat( mr, carr );  
}  
if ( me == 0 ) {  
    printf( "-----" );  
    printf( "-----\nRan OK\n" );  
}  
MPI_Finalize();  
}
```

Appendix 4

```
#include <stdlib.h>
#ifdef GRP // SNIC-LIU modification
#include "tmpic.h"
#else
#include <mpi.h>
#endif
#include "mpiargs.h"
#include "fundefs.h"

void gtrans( int n1, int n2, int m1, int m2,
            double **ar, double **ai, double **atr, double **ati,
            int dir, double *time )
// -----
// 'gtrans' does a global transposition of arrays 'ar' & 'ai' and
// puts them in arrays 'atr' & 'ati'.
// -----
{
    MPI_Comm comm = MPI_COMM_WORLD;
    double **wrkr, **wrk2r, **wrki, **wrk2i;
// SNIC-LIU modification. The arrays scnts etc. are now defined in
// mpiargs.h #####
// int *scnts, *sdpls, *rcnts, *rdpls;
// #####
    double *bufin, *bufout;
    double ltime;
// -----
// --- If nodes = 1, only local transposition.

    if ( nodes == 1 ) {
        ltrans( n1, n2, ar, ai, atr, ati );
        return;
    }
// -----
// --- Make work arrays.

    wrkr = makmat( n2, m1 ); wrki = makmat( n2, m1 );
    bufin = calloc( n2*m1, sizeof( double ) );
    bufout = calloc( n1*m2, sizeof( double ) );
// SNIC-LIU modification. The below part is moved out of gtrans #####
// scnts = calloc( nodes, sizeof( int ) );
// sdpls = calloc( nodes, sizeof( int ) );
// rcnts = calloc( nodes, sizeof( int ) );
// rdpls = calloc( nodes, sizeof( int ) );
// #####
// -----
// --- Do local transpositions first.

    ltrans( m1, n2, ar, ai, wrkr, wrki );
// -----
// --- Determine sizes and displacements of data to be sent.
```

```

// SNIC-LIU modification. The below part is moved out of gtrans #####
// cntdpls( scnts, sdpls, rcnts, rdpls, dir );
// #####
// -----
// --- Distribute appropriate blocks over the processors and do a block
// transposition on the output buffers afterwards to get the
// elements of 'at[rj]' in the right order.

    d2to1( n2, m1, wrkr, bufin );
    ltime = MPI_Wtime();
#ifdef GRP // SNIC-LIU modification
    MPI_Alltoallv_tuned(bufin, gr_scnt, gr_sdis, bufout, gr_rcnt, gr_rdis, GMPI_COMM_WORLD);
#else
    MPI_Alltoallv( bufin, scnts, sdpls, MPI_DOUBLE,
                  bufout, rcnts, rdpls, MPI_DOUBLE, comm );
#endif
    btrans( n1, n2, bufout, atr, dir );
    d2to1( n2, m1, wrki, bufin );
#ifdef GRP // SNIC-LIU modification
    MPI_Alltoallv_tuned(bufin, gr_scnt, gr_sdis, bufout, gr_rcnt, gr_rdis, GMPI_COMM_WORLD);
#else
    MPI_Alltoallv( bufin, scnts, sdpls, MPI_DOUBLE,
                  bufout, rcnts, rdpls, MPI_DOUBLE, comm );
#endif
    btrans( n1, n2, bufout, ati, dir );
    *time = *time + MPI_Wtime() - ltime;
// -----
// --- Clean up.

    free( bufin ); free( bufout );
// SNIC-LIU modification. The below part is moved out of gtrans #####
// free( scnts ); free( sdpls ); free( rcnts ); free( rdpls );
// #####
    delmat( m2, wrki ); delmat( m2, wrkr );
}

```

19/03